

**PERCEPTIONS OF TEACHERS ON MEDIA USE IN TEACHING
AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS
IN KAKAMEGA EAST, SUB COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

Media enhanced interest of learners enlivened the classroom and improved learning outcome. Despite use of media in teaching and learning, English language registered dismal performance in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examinations in Kakamega East Sub-County, Kenya. The decline was attributed to inappropriate and non-use of media in the curriculum. The purpose of the study was to establish perceptions of teachers on media use in teaching and learning of English language in public secondary schools in Kakamega East Sub-County. Specific objective of the study was to establish: perceptions of teachers on media use in teaching and learning of English language. The study revealed that teaching while incorporating appropriate media enhanced academic performance in the curriculum. The study used descriptive survey design. Romiszowski (1992) Conceptual Framework was used to establish perceptions of teachers on media use in teaching and learning of English language. The study population consisted of 23 head teachers, 46 teachers of English and 1500 Form Two students. Saturated sampling technique was used to select a sample of 20 head teachers and 40 teachers of English. Simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 500 Form Two students. Piloting of instruments was done on 10% of

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the population. Research instruments were questionnaire, document analysis guide, observation schedule and interview schedule. Content validity was attained by presenting research instruments to three experts in Department of Educational Communication Technology and Curriculum Studies. Quantitative data was collected from closed questionnaire items which were tallied and presented using frequency counts, percentages and means. Qualitative data was transcribed and organized into categories, subcategories and themes. The findings of the study showed that media use enabled learners to conceptualize abstract concepts and increased rate of retention in the curriculum. The study therefore recommended that teachers should use media appropriately to improve learning outcome in teaching and learning of English language.

Keywords: media use/teaching aids, learning outcome

Abbreviations:

ICT - Information and Communication Technology,

ETQ - English Teachers Questionnaire,

LQ - Learners Questionnaire,

ROK - Republic of Kenya.

1. Introduction

Media involved use of video tapes, phones, computer software, CD-ROMs, television (TV), camera and overhead projectors (OHP) in the curriculum (Smaldino et al., 2008). Studies have shown that media facilitated communication and enhanced teaching and learning in the classroom (George, 1995). Instructional media made spoken words clear during teaching and learning (Curzon, 2002). According to Dahama & Dhatnagar (1992), students learned 25% to 30% more when visual aids were used in teaching. Instructional media held attention of learners, increased permanence of learning and made the job of teaching easier. Certainly, instructional media increased rate of conceptualization in the curriculum (Akinpelu, 1991). In spite of these developments, teachers tended to teach theoretically without much regard to incorporating media in their teaching process (Runaku, 1996).

The study of Ambuko (2008) revealed that appropriate use of media enhanced teaching of Kiswahili language in Emuhaya District, Kenya. However, Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) reported English language performance had declined (KNEC, 2000). The scenario had not changed much in Kakamega East Sub - County where students' performance in English language had shown a downward trend. Specifically, the study: identified perceptions of teachers on media use in teaching and learning of English language.

Consequently, the following question was formulated to direct the study:

- What are perceptions of teachers on media use in teaching and learning of English language?

2. Methodology

The study used descriptive survey design. Saturated sampling was used to select 20 head teachers and 40 teachers of English. Simple random sampling method was used to select a sample of 500 Form Two students from a population of 1500. The sample, therefore, consisted of 20 head teachers, 40 teachers of English and 500 Form Two students. The main data collection instrument was questionnaire, one administered to students, another to headteachers and finally to teachers of English. Questionnaire was preferred because it provided confidentiality hence gave a room for more information regarding use of media in teaching and learning of English language. Interview schedule was administered to teachers of English while lesson observation schedule confirmed the results from the questionnaires. Document analysis guide provided relevant information on acquisition and utilization of instructional media in English language teaching and learning. The study used test-retest (coefficient of stability) method to estimate degree of reliability of the instruments. The computed coefficients of reliability were 0.78, 0.80 and 0.85 for the questionnaires for students, head teachers and teachers of English respectively. The computed coefficient of reliability for the interview schedules was 0.85 for the teachers of English. The study relied on face validity procedures using three experts. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages and means).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Perceptions of Media Use

The study of Dahama & Bhatnagar (1995) observed that instructional media enhanced learning in the curriculum. Therefore, the current study sought to find out perceptions of teachers on media use in teaching and learning of English language. Teachers observed that media use enhanced understanding of concepts (70%) and made learning enjoyable and interesting (60%) during teaching and learning of English language.

Furthermore, English Teachers Questionnaire (ETQ) sought to find out from teachers the extent to which media use assisted them in realizing lesson objective(s). The findings were summed up in Table 1.

Table 1: Extent Media use Assisted in Realizing Lesson Objective(s)

Extent of Media Use	Response (F)	Percentage (%)
Very Great Extent	21	53.0
Great Extent	10	25.0
Fair Extent	9	22.0
Minimum Extent	0	0.0
No Extent at all	0	0.0

From Table 1, twenty-one teachers (53%), 10 teachers (25%) and nine teachers (22%) indicated that media use assisted them in realizing lesson objective(s) to very great extent,

great extent and fair extent respectively. Therefore, majority of teachers (100%) very great extent (53%) great extent (25%) fair extent (22%) agreed that media use in teaching influenced achievement of the lesson objective(s) in English language. The purpose of instructional media was to facilitate communication, classroom interaction and to enhance learning. Generally, media carried messages with an instructional purpose (Smaldino et al., 2008).

All teachers (100%) agreed that media use influenced students learning of English language. Teachers observed that media use: Made learning memorable (70%), provided life experiences in classroom (50%), set mood in English teaching (55%), made meaning clear (60%) and prevented misunderstanding during teaching and learning (50%). Furthermore, media discouraged students from translating from their first language (60%) and helped learners to develop critical thinking during learning process (60%). The findings were summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Media Influenced Learning of English Language

Influence of Media Use	Number of teachers (F)	Percentage (%)
Made learning memorable	28	70.0
Provided life experiences in classroom	20	50.0
Set mood in English teaching	22	55.0
Made meaning clear	24	60.0
Prevented misunderstanding during teaching and learning	20	50.0
Media discouraged students from translating from their first language	24	60.0
Helped learners to develop critical thinking during learning process	24	60.0

Learner's Questionnaire (LQ) sought to find out from learners whether English concepts were well understood when the teacher uses various instructional resources during teaching. Table 3 showed summary of their responses.

Table 3: Instructional Resources Increased Rate of Understanding

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agreed	400	80.0
Agreed	83	16.6
Undecided	13	2.6
Disagreed	4	0.8
Strongly disagreed	00	0.0

Table 3 indicated that learners were aware of influence of media use in learning of English language. Majority of learners (96.6%) strongly agreed (80%) agreed (16.6%) that English language concepts were well understood when teacher incorporated media during teaching of English language. Furthermore, another question item of LQ revealed 90% of learners strongly agreed (65%) agreed (25%) that use of media in learning of English

language ensured longer retention of content learned. The results depicted that media use in learning promoted memory. Certainly, the results concurred with the observation of ROK (2002); ROK (2006) that instructional media increased retention rate in the curriculum. Learners' respondents observed that failure to use media led to them receiving blurred messages from the teacher. Significantly, Mwangi et al., (2010) observed that appropriate use of media made teacher's explanations clear. They also appreciated that media such as TV simplified language of authors during learning session.

4. Conclusions

4.1 Perceptions of Media Use

The study showed that media use influenced teaching and learning of English language. They enhanced appropriate competences such as knowledge, skills and attitude in the curriculum. Benefits accrued from media use in teaching and learning included: made learning interesting and interactive, promoted peer learning, ensured understanding of abstract concepts and increased retention rate in the curriculum.

5. Policy Recommendations

5.1 Perceptions of Media Use

The study recommended teachers should use media appropriately to improve learning outcome in the English language. Expected learning outcome included: fluent communication and acquisition of English language skills.

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